

STUDIES ON THE FRIES REARRANGEMENT. PART XVI

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The effect of less than a molar proportion of anhydrous aluminium chloride as a catalyst in the Fries rearrangement has been studied. A method of separation of *ortho*- and *para*-hydroxyketones by the chromatographic technique has also been developed.

The effect of more than one molar quantity of the catalyst on the Fries rearrangement has been studied by many workers (Pyman *et al.*, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1930, 280; Thakor and Shah, this *Journal*, 1946, 23, 234; Amin and Shah, *ibid.*, 1948, 26, 377; Tiwari and Tewari, *ibid.*, 1954, 31, 79). But a search in the literature shows that the effect of lesser amount of the catalyst has not been studied earlier. We have therefore investigated the Fries rearrangement of the acetates of phenol, 3-methylphenol, 3-ethylphenol and 2-chloro-4-*tert*-butylphenol, using 0.25 M, 0.5 M, 0.75 M, 1.0 M and 1.25 M of anhydrous aluminium chloride.

It has been found that even with 0.25 M of the catalyst, the total yields of the hydroxyketones are 72-80%. This observation contradicts the usual notion that one mole of the catalyst is required for the Fries migration of one mole of an ester. With lesser amounts of the catalyst, the yields of *para*-hydroxyketone increase with the catalyst concentration. This observation is also contrary to that of Ralston (*J. Org. Chem.*, 1940, 5, 645) that beyond the region of one molar quantity of the catalyst, the yield of *para* isomer diminishes with increase in the catalyst concentration.

EXPERIMENTAL

Fries Rearrangement of the Ester.—The ester (1.0 M) was rearranged by appropriate amount of anhydrous aluminium chloride at 130° for 2 hours, following the procedure of Tiwari and Tewari (*loc. cit.*). In the first three cases, the separation of *ortho* and *para* isomers was effected by steam-distillation. In a few cases only traces of *para* isomers were found to be present. The results are summarised in Table I.

TABLE I

Effect of lesser amount of catalyst.

Temp. = 130°. Time = 2 hours.

Catalyst conc.	Yields of hydroxyketones.						
	<i>ortho</i> . 1. Phenyl acetate.	<i>para</i> .	<i>ortho</i> . 2. 3-Methylphenyl acetate.	<i>para</i> .	<i>ortho</i> . 3. 3-Ethylphenyl acetate.	<i>para</i> .	<i>ortho</i> . 4. 2-Chloro-4- <i>tert</i> -butylphenyl acetate.
0.25 M	80.0%	Trace	72.0%	6.0%	74.0%	Trace	72.0%
0.50	82.0	"	72.0	8.0	78.0	"	74.0
0.75	80.0	4.0%	70.0	10.0	78.0	"	74.0
1.00	74.0	10.0	72.0	12.0	80.0	2.0%	80.0
1.25	70.0	18.0	70.0	16.0	80.0	4.0	82.0

Chromatographic Separation of o- and p-Hydroxyketones.—There are several known methods of separation of *ortho*- and *para*-hydroxyketones from a mixture of both. Each of these methods has its limitations. Hence, we tried chromatographic separation of these isomers using *flowing chromatogram* technique. The Chromatographic method has no special advantage as it provides approximately the same results.

A tube of 2 cm. in diameter and 60 cm. in length was partly filled with dry chloroform and absorbent alumina was added in it carefully until it settled down and a column of 40 cm. was obtained without any air gap.

About 1.5 g. of the known mixture, prepared authentically, or the rearranged product, dissolved in 8 c.c. of dry chloroform, was added to the column. It was gradually drawn in the column. Fresh portions of dry chloroform were added from time to time so that no air was drawn into the upper portion of the column. As the solution was drawn in, a yellow band developed. At first the percolate was colorless, but as soon as the yellow band touched the lowest part of the column, the colour of the percolate turned yellow. A drop of the percolate was then taken on a filter paper and after evaporation of the solvent a drop of 1% ferric chloride solution was added. A blue colour developed at the spot which indicated the presence of the *o*-hydroxyketones. Whole of the percolate responding to the colour test was collected together and the solvent evaporated on a water-bath, when the *o*-hydroxyketone was obtained.

When the percolate ceased to respond to the colour test for the *o*-hydroxyketone, 20 c.c. portions were collected and the solvent evaporated. Usually the first portion yielded nothing. Next portions yielded solid *para* isomers on evaporation of the chloroform. The process was continued with fresh portions of 20 c.c. each until no solid was obtained. All solid portions were collected together and weighed. The results of both the experiments are summarised below.

TABLE II
Chromatographic separation of authentic mixtures.

Hydroxyketones derived from :	Hydroxyketones taken.		Hydroxyketones recovered.	
	<i>ortho</i> .	<i>para</i> .	<i>ortho</i> .	<i>para</i> .
1. Phenyl acetate	1.24 g.	0.34 g.	1.18 g.	0.32 g.
2. 3-Methylphenyl acetate	1.16	0.37	1.12	0.34
3. 3-Ethylphenyl acetate	1.35	0.12	1.32	0.10
4. 2- <i>tert</i> -.Butyl-3-methylphenyl acetate	1.28	0.26	1.24	0.21

TABLE III
Chromatographic separation of rearrangement products.

Hydroxyketones derived from :	Temperature.	% Yield of hydroxyketones by			
		Chromatography.		Steam-distillation.	
		<i>ortho</i> .	<i>para</i> .	<i>ortho</i> .	<i>para</i> .
Phenyl acetate	130°	74.0	21.0	70.0	18.0
3-Methylphenyl acetate	130°	74.0	19.0	70.0	16.0

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